

ANALYSIS-ENABLED PRODUCTION AND PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITE WING STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A strategic partnership between a major Tier One supplier of high-performance composite aero-structures and a university composites research group is described. The partnership stems from secondment of the second author to the company under a Royal Academy of Engineering scheme. It subsequently led to a five-year RAEng Research Chair in Composites Analysis, commencing in 2013. The research programme for the Chair covers work in process and performance modelling, laminate optimisation and in steered fibre design. The paper indicates that analysis developments, such as new FE formulations for pre-cured layer deformation, characterisation of process properties and detailed analysis of edge-driven failure in test coupons, can quickly influence the manufacture and certification of production parts. However, changes to conventional laminate design rules are more difficult to implement, despite demonstrating significant improvement in manufacturing quality and a potential for saving in structural weight. Here, close collaboration with the OEM is required in order to advance new methods through the TRL process and bring significant benefit to future certified designs.

1 INTRODUCTION

GKN Aerospace is a first tier supplier to the global aviation industry, providing full design, development, manufacture, assembly, integration and certification of primary and secondary structures and components across civil, military and UAV platforms. The company has expertise in metallic and composite materials, automated manufacturing processes, such as automated fibre placement (AFP) and tape lay (ATL), and assembly technologies delivering high performance products such as leading and trailing edges, wing boxes and vertical and horizontal tail-planes. It is engaged in multiple research programmes across metallic and composite box structures, novel manufacturing processes and performance enhancements such as natural laminar flow and ice phobic coatings.

The Composites Research Unit (CRU) at the University of Bath investigates the mechanical behaviour of composite materials and lightweight structures and exploits this understanding for use in design and manufacture. The CRU comprises one professor, two early career academics, a post-doctoral researcher and six PhD students.

The partnership between GKN and the University of Bath started when the second author undertook a Royal Academy of Engineering (RAEng) secondment with the company throughout 2011. In 2013, the second author was awarded a 5-year RAEng/GKN Research Chair in composites analysis with a research programme covering 5 work packages which mirror the composite design and manufacture cycle, see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Industrial design and manufacturing cycle (outer ring) and university research programme (inner ring).

Fig. 2 The influence of steered fibre radius and Discrete Angle strips on optimum mass of a 250mm wide compression panel. Crosses indicate limits of manufacturability.

The partnership has led to significant investment in composites research at the University of Bath, a range of research opportunities, new links with the university's Department of Mathematical Sciences plus opportunities for staff and students. This paper illustrates the impact that the close working relationship between academia and industry has had on the development of expertise and Intellectual Property by both GKN Aerospace and the University of Bath. In order to illustrate these points, each of the development sectors identified in Figure 1 is considered in turn, starting with laminate optimisation.

2 RESEARCH PROGRAMME

2.1 Laminate Optimisation

Laminate design is governed by the Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) and is based on 'rules' which have been long established and have been proven in many applications. These include: the use of four standard ply angles (0, 90, +45 and -45 degrees), enforced symmetry about the mid-plane, grouping together (blocking) of no more than 3 plies of the same angle, and a minimum of 10% of material in each of the standard ply directions. However, it is apparent that some rules may prevent a more efficient laminate design being used. Manufacturing concepts such as tow steering or non-standard ply angles are not encompassed within these rules. For example, as shown in Fig. 2, when the design is driven by a buckling constraint, steering can produce mass savings approaching 40%. Clearly, strength, damage resistance and damage tolerance should not be compromised and university studies have also explored these criteria [1,2].

The first generation of large civil aircraft, where a substantial part of the structure is in composite, have been designed with conservatism. It is therefore likely that the first opportunity to deploy optimisation technology (and in effect push beyond the traditional rules) will be on developments of these first generation aircraft where the operating cases are well understood and the actual performance capability is well characterized. There will be a strong incentive to improve the efficiency of the developed version to increase payload and range without major changes to the design and to the manufacturing tooling. The ability to enhance performance by optimizing laminate design will be a key advantage here. In order to carry out this optimisation the value of weight saving or performance improvement must be defined.

Another important factor is the ability to resolve manufacturing problems through changes to the laminate stack. A GKN-funded PhD has demonstrated the benefit of anti-symmetric laminate designs [3] leading to a reduction in springback distortion and improved consolidation of the laminates. Further benefits to manufactured part quality may be gained through the use of optimisation analysis based on a level of understanding of the influence of laminate design on part manufacturing quality.

Clearly, the deployment in mainline design is dependent on the product development cycle being in phase with the technology's Technology Readiness Level (TRL). It is also dependent on the cooperation of the OEM for the target application. However, GKN have already started to take advantage of laminate optimisation technology in the research phase: The University of Bath have contributed towards the demonstration of new laminate designs in the following research applications: (i) the Advanced Winglet manufactured in the TSB sponsored Structures Technology Maturity Project (SteM) project, (ii) a sub-scale spar demonstrator manufactured as part of a PhD programme [3] and (iii) the panel buckling evaluated in the Aerostructural Efficiency of Damage Tolerant Composites via Optimised Fibre Placement (ABBSTRACT) project.

2.2 Forming and Folding

GKN's aerostructures business is increasingly focused on the production of wing primary structures and components. In order to produce parts at a high rate with a high level of consistency and quality, GKN employ composite prepreg material laid down by automated fibre deposition techniques. In a subsequent step, the material is formed or consolidated onto mandrels immediately prior to curing. Over the last 10 years, the company has made a large investment in the development and implementation of these manufacturing processes in production. As a result, a considerable amount of 'know-how' relating to the technology has been built up. Nevertheless, GKN are aware that there is scope to further improve deposition, forming, folding and consolidation operations to deliver consistent product. The manufacturing process is administered by GKN as part of its key offering as a Tier One supplier. The company may investigate and propose manufacturing process improvements to be agreed by the OEM. These improvements can be made without affecting cured composite properties and as a result can be introduced without extensive requalification.

Since the start of the RAEng-sponsored collaboration between GKN and the University of Bath, the acquisition of manufacturing experience has been complemented by research, undertaken by the university, into prepreg material behaviour in the uncured state. This understanding of the forming process map and key process variables can be deployed in the following ways: (i) the selection of forming and debulk process times and temperatures, (ii) the investigation of defect generation in current product, (iii) the study of future manufacturing options for a Next Generation Aircraft and (iv) to support current development manufacturing activities such as the EU Clean Sky funded, Breakthrough Laminar Aircraft Demonstrator (BLADE) project, and the ATI funded Validation and Integration of Manufacturing Enablers for Future Wing Structures (VIEWS) project.

Deployment of the technology in this way is not dependent on a validation process and GKN are already benefitting from this technology. Feedback from deployment will refine and improve the methodology – this experience becomes key GKN 'know-how'.

A good example is the work on slip characterisation that has been undertaken [5] to study the mechanics of forming operations. If laminates are to conform to a surface with curvature during forming or consolidation, plies within the laminate must shear relative to each other. If plies are prevented from shearing the process becomes susceptible to generating a host of defects including ply wrinkling, part distortion and poor consolidation. To limit the formation of such defects, the characterisation of the shear properties of the composite laminate in the uncured state is vital. This work is described in detail elsewhere but it is sufficient to state here that the University of Bath results

are underpinning forming and consolidation rules which are being implemented on current production parts.

A corner wrinkling model [6] provided the first indication of mechanical properties that influence the formation of wrinkles for specific geometry. These properties have been characterised in the generic experimental study, [5] which established the conditions for minimum resistance to inter-laminar slip, see Fig. 3. A recently developed Cosserat element [7, 8] captures the deformation of multiple layers of pre-cured laminate, Fig. 4 (top). This enables generic process modelling at significantly reduced computational cost compared with conventional FEA, in which elements must be refined to capture inter-laminar deformation Fig. 4 (bottom).

Fig. 3 Minimization of critical inter laminar shear stress τ_c maximizes pre-preg mobility [5]

Fig. 4 Cosserat model of slip in bending of four layers (top) compared with conventional FEA (bottom).

2.3 Imaging, Stochastics and Failure Analysis

These topics relate to predicting the performance of the manufactured product taking into account the types of material defect and variability in microstructure that may be encountered within the population of manufactured parts. The university work in this area is aimed at the accurate characterisation of defects using tools such as computer aided tomography (CT scanning). The information is to be linked in an automated way to a finite element representation of a defect so that an analysis of the defect and its local effects can be carried out. A computationally efficient method for combining the local effects into a global (FE) performance prediction is the subject of an EPSRC Maths for Manufacturing Multi-scale Analysis project at the University of Bath (EP/K031368/1). This project also includes a probabilistic approach to defect severity and location based on measured distributions.

While these methods of performance prediction are currently at a low TRL, they cannot be used in isolation for certified designs without substantial validation. However, they are already providing fundamental data for understanding composite materials behaviour. CT imaging techniques applied to defects detected in production can be used to refine the defect definitions in the Quality Acceptance Standard for parts. Where predicted behaviour may be confirmed by test, defect characterisation can support concession applications for defects falling outside the standard limits. In the longer term, the probabilistic approach will be used to reduce the level of testing required for part certification.

When detected defects can be extracted so that they are contained within coupons for mechanical testing then there is the opportunity to validate the prediction tools. Such defects are imaged prior to test and a performance prediction carried out which can be compared with the test result.

The extensive GKN property database, based on mechanical testing for qualification and production monitoring and amounting to many thousands of individual test results, is being used to validate the stochastic models. The stochastic analysis methods are being used to help understand test results at the extremes of the distribution and how they relate to the manufacturing process. In the near future it is envisaged that these methods will be employed to gain efficiencies in the formulation of test programmes to reduce the size of the programmes and lower costs.

For instance, the University of Bath have provided an important understanding relating to the Corner Bend Strength (CBS) tests carried out for production control of manufactured wing spars. GKN suspected that the edges of corner bend test specimens had significant effect on strength of part. FEA investigations conducted at the University of Bath confirmed that this was the case but also showed that the stress singularity at edge made numerical convergence difficult. A resin edge treatment (see Fig. 5) improved test strength and also improved convergence of the FE model, giving confidence in the numerical modelling method. Imaging results on failed coupons is providing substantiating evidence of the predicted failure behaviour [9]. Once sufficient confidence has been gained by industry in the reliability of the analysis of coupons then the method may be extended to modelling full size parts as discussed in the next section.

Fig. 5a CT image of a failed CBS test coupon with resin edge treatment showing delamination above ply level 5

Fig. 5b Corresponding FE model of a CBS coupon in Fig. 5a showing stress concentration at ply level 5 & 6.

2.4 Structural Applications

Multiscale methods for performance analysis are in development jointly by the Department of Mechanical Engineering and Department of Mathematical Sciences at the University of Bath in partnership with GKN Aerospace in an EPSRC, Maths for Manufacturing Multi-scale Analysis project (EP/K031368/1). It is important that these methods are co-developed with the OEM in order to allow their use in the design and manufacture of certified parts. The aim would be to deploy the methods on the Next Generation Aircraft with the design ultimately validated by fewer structural tests.

The development of multiscale methods has the potential to revolutionise composite structural design analysis methods. In the next generation of aircraft, progress in design optimisation will only be made if the analysis is able to handle the full size and complexity of the composite design. Considering the current maturity of these methods, the earliest opportunity to employ these new methods could be 'stretch' variants of existing aircraft. In this case it may be possible to analyse the complete structural response and demonstrate a higher allowable.

Multi-scale methods will be essential in the case that a defect tolerant design philosophy is adopted. The ability to model both the influence of the defect on the local stress state and how it interacts with the global performance will be critical. Similarly in bonded structures, whether composite or metallic, the global performance is ultimately dictated by fracture initiation at a local feature which must be modelled at high fidelity.

Multi-scale models are being employed in current research projects to design technology demonstrators. Manufacturing and testing of these demonstrators during the research phase will provide validating data. For instance, the wing cover for the Clean Sky 'BLADE' project required compensation for spring-back in order to achieve the desired surface profile to support natural laminar flow. A full 3D composite analysis was carried out by GKN to predict the thermal stress state and the resultant deflected shape. From this analysis the compensated mould shape was derived.

3 DISCUSSION

It has been found that the strategic partnership of a technology-driven aerospace supplier and a university research group is hugely beneficial to both parties. The company influences the direction of academic research whilst the university establishes direct routes to impact and funding. However, the strategy has highlighted the following issues which form important principles for synergistic operation of such a partnership.

Academic research is best aimed at understanding the fundamental principles of engineering science, applied to the development of new technology. Industrial application of this understanding is the responsibility of the company. This requires a level of patience when industrial solutions are required in the short term. However, such an approach pays long-term dividends. The distinction also clarifies the boundary between publishable, publically-funded work (key drivers for academia) and commercially sensitive product development. If the university becomes directly involved in product-specific issues, there is a danger of blurring this boundary, potentially leading to ineffective development and problematic publication. Industrial problems are often more complex than can be fully represented in either the research lab or the simulation model. Unravelling this application-driven complexity should, in most cases, be the domain of the industrial engineer, informed by the fundamental academic work.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper the authors have described how University research, nominally at TRL levels 1 to 3, is applied at the concept, design, manufacturing development and production cycle of an aircraft product. They show that low TRL technologies emerging from academic, analysis-related research, as yet unvalidated by the comprehensive testing required by TRL 6 and above can, in fact, be deployed to great effect at all stages of development.

For GKN, the toolkit of analytical methods being developed by the University of Bath has already found application in the IP-rich environment of manufacturing method improvement. As a 'Tier One supplier', GKN has the opportunity to introduce manufacturing process improvements which reduce or eliminate manufacturing defects and improve the quality of the product. A number of manufacturing process improvements implemented by the company have been guided and supported by the results of the Bath research.

Furthermore, the authors have described how the insights provided by the analytical toolkit can inform the initial concept and final design stages for which the aircraft Prime Manufacturer (e.g. Airbus, Boeing, Bombardier, Embraer) hold responsibility. However, application relating to design is more challenging to implement because of the difficulty in changing established laminate design rules. The University of Bath and GKN are therefore encouraging close collaboration with the OEMs to promote the development of these technologies through the TRL process in order to fully deploy the methods in certified designs and exploit improved process and performance.

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